

Employing a Research Community Network to Assess RSE Impact

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Motivation

- Recurring investment in large-scale computation maintains the need for various means to identify **ROI**
- **Collaboration** is increasingly made a priority by universities seeking to pursue larger and more various funding opportunities that require teams of investigators
- Can we apply collaboration metrics to assess impact of **RSEs**?

Dataset

- Dimensions data 2012-2022
 - 137M Publications: Coauthors
 - 7M Awards: Coinvestigators
 - 155M Patents: Coinventors
- Research Software Engineer flag
 - Search on university site for titles:
 - "Research Software Engineer", "Scientific Software Engineer", "Data Scientist", etc.
 - Identified research faculty and post-docs with accounts on ASU Research Computing clusters

Including external collaborations

Consolidated external collaborators into
587 "university" nodes

~98% now in Giant Component

Edges increase from 55,362 to 104,394

Researchers with RSE flag in **yellow** (281)

Comparing node cohorts - centralities

Calculate measures of individual nodes

Degree – raw count of edges

Comparing node cohorts - centralities

Calculate measures of individual nodes

Degree – raw count of edges

Betweenness centrality – "bridge"-ness of node

Small Worlds

- Network structure defined by 2 ratios to random Erdős-Renyi network
- Robustness to node removal
- Small densely connected subnetworks with "bridge nodes"

Comparing node cohorts - centralities

Measure	Mean		<i>p</i> -value
	RC nodes	Non-RC nodes	
Degree	19.8	9.79	<0.001
Betweenness centrality	2.9×10^{-4}	6.4×10^{-5}	<0.001

Analysis of "Research Software Engineers" – a group that is dispersed across the university with little centralized organization or funding.

Measure	Mean		<i>p</i> -value
	RSE nodes	Non-RSE nodes	
Degree	15.63	11.09	<0.001
Betweenness centrality	8.1×10^{-5}	9.6×10^{-5}	<0.001

